

FEM ANALYSIS OF MIXED MODE FRACTURE IN THE IOSIPESCU
SHEAR TEST

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ABSTRACT

Use of the Iosipescu shear test for studying two-dimensional mixed mode fracture behaviour of aligned composite materials is investigated. A finite element analysis is conducted to determine the stress distribution in the specimen before failure assuming two different boundary conditions and orthotropy ratios ranging from 1 to 14.2. The analysis is extended to specimens with two axial splits at the roots of the notches growing along the fibre direction. It is shown that the shear stress concentration at the roots of the notches can be described by a simple numerical relationship in terms of the orthotropy ratio for both boundary conditions considered. The numerical fracture mechanics analysis revealed that the stable propagation of two axial splits from the notches is almost entirely due to Mode I fracture with the critical energy release rate $G_{(I, II)c}$ estimated to be 230 Jm^{-2} for glass/polyester unidirectional lamina.

INTRODUCTION

Fracture of composite materials under combined asymmetric Mode I and antisymmetric Mode II has received considerable attention recently [1,2,5]. An understanding of the relative importance of mixed mode fracture processes of structural composites is useful in developing material properties that can be utilised in a design scheme involving delamination.

The specific objectives of this research are to:

- (1) develop a suitable experimental method to study the mixed mode fracture behaviour of a unidirectional lamina.
- (2) explore the applicability of linear elastic fracture mechanics to the mixed mode fracture of composites.

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The Iosipescu specimen [3], originally developed for shear-property measurements was used to study the problem. The validity of using the specimen for measurement of static shear stiffness and strength of unidirectional laminae has been widely investigated [4,6-8]. However, there are only few published results concerned with fracture mechanics studies employing this test method [9].

The present study is based on the finite element method which has become an attractive tool for numerical calculations associated with linear elastic fracture mechanics. The method is used to determine the stress distribution in the Iosipescu specimen before cracks are formed. The effect of loading boundary conditions and elastic properties on the stress is investigated. Particular attention is given to the problem of two axial splits formed at the roots of the notches in the specimen. The direct finite element approach to fracture mechanics is applied with the stress intensity factors calculated directly from numerical displacements at the crack tip.

TEST PROCEDURE

The Iosipescu shear test achieves a region of pure shear at the centre of a specimen by application of two counteracting moments produced by two force couples [3]. The configuration of the specimen is essentially a beam with two 90° notches cut to a depth of 20 to 25% of the specimen height. For the described specimen geometry and loading conditions the shear stress distribution between the notches is nearly uniform for isotropic material [3] and is equal to the applied shear force divided by the net cross-section area. A means of applying the shear loading to the specimen was proposed by Adams and Walrath [6-8], see Fig.1.

Fig.1 Schematic representation of loading fixture for Iosipescu shear test [6,7]

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

The finite element method was used to determine displacements and stresses in the Iosipescu specimen employing the finite element package PAFEC. The elastic properties used are shown in Table 1. Two material orientations with respect to the specimen coordinates were assumed. In orientation A the fibre orientation is parallel to the X-axis of the specimen and in B the fibre direction is parallel to the Y-axis (see Fig.2).

TABLE 1
Elastic properties of the materials used in the finite element analysis

material	polyester resin	glass fibre polyester	carbon fibre epoxy
E_{11}/E_{22}	1	3.45	14.2
E_{11} [GN/m ²]	3.6	37	137.9
E_{22} [GN/m ²]	3.6	10.7	9.7
ν_{12}	0.36	0.27	0.32
G_{12} [GN/m ²]	1.4	4.4	4.2

The loading of the model simulated two different boundary conditions:

- (a) the loading originally proposed by Iosipescu with two force couples applied to the specimen as presented in Fig.2a (force couple condition).
- (b) the displacement boundary conditions applied by Walrath and Adams [8] (displacement condition, see Fig.2b).

In the second case, the boundary conditions were assumed in such a way that there was no rotation of the ends of the specimen in the loading fixture.

STRESS DISTRIBUTION IN THE IOSIPESCU SPECIMEN BEFORE FAILURE

A particular feature of the stress distribution in the Iosipescu specimen is the shear stress concentration at the notch root which is highly dependent upon the elastic properties of the tested material and the notch geometry [8]. In this study the shear stress concentration is analysed in terms of different orthotropy ratio E_{11}/E_{22} and two boundary conditions previously mentioned. The variation of the shear stress

Fig.2 Boundary conditions assumed for finite element calculations
 (a) force couple conditions (b) displacement conditions

concentration factor K_t , defined as the ratio of the shear stress at the notch root to the stress in the centre of the specimen, with orthotropy ratio and specimen configuration is shown in Fig.3 on a logarithmic scale. These results indicate that there is a simple relationship between K_t and orthotropy ratio given by

$$K_t = A (E_{11}/E_{22})^{1/4} \quad (1)$$

where A is a numerical factor describing the shear stress concentration in an isotropic specimen. In the ideal case, the factor should be equal to 1 for the isotropic specimen. However, the small shear stress concentration is caused by the induced compressive stresses from the external applied load. The influence of the compressive stresses in the neighbourhood of the notches is more significant in the displacement condition ($K_t = 1.18$) than for the force couple condition ($K_t = 1.07$).

The finite element analysis has also shown that the uniformity of the shear stress field in the centre of the specimen along the X axis also depends on the orthotropy ratio and the boundary conditions. A uniform pure shear stress region should contain two principal stresses at 45° to the vertical line between the notches. Any deviation from this angle is related to the presence of normal stresses. Fig.4(a) and Fig.4(b) present

Fig.3 Effect of orthotropy ratio E_{11}/E_{22} on shear stress concentrations at notch root K_t for A and B orientations and two boundary conditions considered.

the angle α between the principal stress σ_2 and the notch-root axis plotted for the force couple and displacement conditions respectively. The results presented suggest that any constraints applied to the ends of the specimen to prevent their rotation in the loading fixture will increase normal stresses in the specimen centre (Fig.4b). Moreover, it is apparent that the specimen with B-type fibre orientation provides more uniform shear stress in the test section, particularly for high orthotropy ratios.

Fig.4 Angle α between principal stress σ_2 and notch root axis plotted from specimen centre along X axis for A and B orientations and different orthotropy ratios (a) force couple condition, (b) displacement condition.

MIXED MODE FRACTURE IN GLASS/POLYESTER SPECIMEN

Fracture of unidirectional glass/polyester specimens [4] with A-type fibre orientation resulted in the formation of two approximately symmetric cracks 3 to 5mm in length (see Fig.5(a) and (b)). These cracks were located immediately adjacent to the tips of the notches on the opposite sides to the points of the applied load. Because of the constraints imposed by the fibres the cracks grew in the same plane up to a maximum length of 6mm during further loading of the specimen. At the same time a second type of failure from the roots of the notches at an angle slightly away from the fibre normal was formed. The failure appears as two damage zones consisting of numerous cracks along the fibre/matrix interfaces [5].

The cracks growing from the roots of the notches in glass/polyester specimen were modelled using the finite element mesh. The finite element mesh used was highly refined at the areas containing two crack tips. The elements attached to the crack tip were the collapsed triangular quarter-point isoparametric elements [10] which give rise to square-root singular stresses in these regions making it possible to obtain accurate values of the stress intensity factors.

Fig.5 Typical force/deflection diagram (a) for glass/polyester specimen with A-type fibre orientation [4] and (b) failure geometry.

Fig.6 Deformation of (a) entire mesh and (b) inner mesh with 6mm long cracks and force couple condition.

Fig.6(a) shows as an example the entire finite element mesh with two cracks of equal length after deformation for force couple condition. For the same loading the inner mesh containing the crack tip elements are shown in Fig.6(b). It is apparent from the finite element results in Fig.6(b) that the displacements around the crack tip exhibit mixed mode fracture conditions. From the numerical displacements of the node situated at a distance of one element from the crack tip the mixed mode stress intensity factors K_I and K_{II} were calculated for both isotropic and orthotropic models and various crack lengths. The known analytical

relationships [11] between the stress intensity factors and the displacement field at the crack tip for an orthotropic model were used. The factors for the specimen with force couple condition are presented in Fig.7.

Fig.7 Stress intensity factors K_I and K_{II} computed for different orthotropy ratios versus crack length for force couple condition.

The results demonstrate that K_I and K_{II} are strongly dependent upon the orthotropy ratio. For E_{11}/E_{22} greater than 1 the stress intensity factor K_I is smaller than K_{II} for the whole range of crack lengths considered. One point which should be mentioned here is the fact that the factors calculated for an isotropic specimen do not have any physical meaning since such cracks cannot exist in the real case. The factors have been shown only in order to compare the results for all orthotropy ratios considered.

Generally speaking, self-similar mixed mode cracks cannot be effectively described by a single fracture mechanics parameter related to one particular fracture mode. When both G_I and G_{II} are present, the types of failure are likely to be governed by their relative magnitude and the onset of crack growth should occur when the total energy release rate $G_{(I,II)}$ given by

$$G_{(I,II)} = G_I + G_{II} \quad (2)$$

reaches a critical value $G_{(I,II)c}$.

For orthotropic materials with cracks in the principal material directions the energy release rates for Mode I and II fracture are given by [11].

$$G_I = K_I^2 \left(\frac{a_{11} a_{22}}{2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[\left(\frac{a_{22}}{a_{11}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{2a_{12} + a_{66}}{2a_{11}} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (3)$$

$$G_{II} = K_{II}^2 \frac{a_{11}}{\sqrt{2}} \left[\left(\frac{a_{22}}{a_{11}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{2a_{12} + a_{66}}{2a_{11}} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

when a_{ij} - are anisotropic compliances which can be calculated from the elastic properties in Table I.

Values of $G_{(I,II)}$ were calculated for glass/polyester system (Fig.8) using equations (2) and (3). Two boundary conditions were considered. The

Fig.8 Mixed mode energy release rate $G_{(I,II)} = G_I + G_{II}$ as a function of crack length for force couple and displacement conditions.

stress intensity factors in equation (3) were determined for the forces and displacements recorded at specimen failure (Fig.5(a)). The differences between force couple conditions and the displacement conditions are not significant for crack lengths smaller than 5mm. For longer cracks the differences are more pronounced and $G_{(I,II)}$ is greater for the force couple condition. Thus, from the results the mixed-mode material fracture toughness $G_{(I,II)c}$ can be evaluated at the onset of stable crack growth. The stable crack growth was usually observed between 4 to 6mm. For a

crack length of 4mm the estimated value of $G_{(I,II)c} = 230\text{Jm}^{-2}$. This implies that the stable crack propagation is due to Mode I fracture since the critical energy release rate $G_{Ic} = 120\text{Jm}^{-2}$ compared with $G_{IIc} = 3.5\text{kJm}^{-2}$ [5].

CONCLUSIONS

1. Stress distributions within the Iosipescu shear specimen are highly dependent on both the elastic properties and boundary conditions assumed.
2. The shear stress concentration at the notch root of the specimen can be described by the following numerical relationship $K_t = A (E_{11}/E_{22})^{1/4}$ in terms of orthotropy ratio and the shear stress concentration in isotropic specimens.
3. The failure of the Iosipescu specimen with A-type fibre orientation is associated with the formation of two axial splits at the notches. Finite element results have indicated that the displacements at the crack tip exhibit mixed mode fracture conditions with K_{II} significantly greater than K_I for all crack lengths considered.
4. The energy release rate $G_{(I,II)} = G_I + G_{II}$ has been calculated for glass/polyester unidirectional lamina. The results have shown that the fracture mode is predominantly of Mode I with $G_{(I,II)c} = 230\text{Jm}^2 \approx G_{Ic}$ at the onset of stable crack propagation.

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